

Rehabilitation of Post Covid Mucormycosis Maxillectomy Defect With Hollow Obturator

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Pre-operative intra-oral picture of maxillary defect

Primary Impression and cast was made.

Custom tray fabricated using self-cure acrylic resin.

Final Impression made with light body impression material and master cast was made

2mm thickness of wax was adapted and putty index was made. Investing and dewaxing was done.

Packing was done using heat-cure acrylic resin with salt in between to make a hollow design.

Weight of obturator before and after salt removal.

Insertion of the Obturator.

A 40-year old male patient reported to the OPD with a chief complaint of difficulty in eating, drinking and speaking. He had undergone maxillectomy due to post covid mucormycosis 1 year back.

Treatment plan: Definitive hollow bulb obturator. It was made hollow to reduce the weight of the obturator. Primary and final impressions were taken and cast was formed. The hollow bulb was made with lost salt technique to reduce the weight.